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Inclusivity across Sectors

Uileghabhálacht Thar Earnálacha

Embedding equality, diversity, and inclusion in GLAM structures with digital storytelling

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Outline

Background:

- EDI in GLAMs
- The “participatory turn” and digital storytelling (DS)

Case study at Shanghai Library:

- ‘Shanghai Cultural Collection’ project
- Methodological framework

Summary:

- How DS supports EDI in GLAM structures?
 - Our expectations
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EDI in GLAMs

EDI (or 'DEI' in US) is included as an institutional strategy by many GLAM institutions, specifically to ensure the **allowing and respecting of differences, diversities, human rights and freedoms**, building upon **shared understanding of fairness, dignity, and respect** (CILIP, 2018; ALA, 2017).

GLAMS and their parent organizations are often perceived as engaging in a **limited** set of diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) activities, specifically:

“collection highlights” [e.g., announcements on website or book displays],

“public events or programs” ,

“optional employee training/professional development” (Ho, Schiff, & Deng, 2023).

The “participatory turn” and digital storytelling

Digital storytelling: a movement or method for creating, expressing, interpreting, and sharing stories and personal experiences using digital tools, has been viewed as a "**democratization of culture.**" (Clarke & Adam, 2011)

Well-crafted stories can communicate abstract and complex ideas in ways that **encourage understanding;**

Effective stories inspire people by creating **human connection** and **emotional resonance** (Rockefeller Foundation 2014).

As an approach to construct and express meaning, storytelling can also be seen as a process of **reconstructing memory, the past as well as the culture** of individuals, groups, and communities (Fu, Mahony & Liu, 2023).

Figure source:
<http://www.thehealthcarepeople.com/storytelling-powerful-leadership-tool/>

The “participatory turn” and digital storytelling

The research on digital storytelling has evolved from the early exploration of diverse narrative formats, through the uncertainty of technological development, to scholars' attempting to break away from traditional narrative theories and construct new theoretical frameworks to interpret this new narrative paradigm (Cunsolo et al., 2013).

The virtual space that is formed with the practice of digital storytelling is defined as a “shared infrastructure” by Couldry (2008) where individuals and communities can express and reflect upon stories that ultimately work towards “invigorating the community thereby encouraging participation” (Conrad 2013, p.262).

The application of digital storytelling in promoting EDI has proven effective in areas such as the **exploration of collective religious group identity** (Clark & Dierberg, 2012), and **providing services for disabled groups** (Bliss & Fisher, 2013).

Shanghai Cultural Collection

- Knowledge extracted: people, organization, geographical name, architecture, event
- Diverse memory forms organized and linked by knowledge
- Help users to discover stories through memory materials

Shanghai city 1825-1949

Photos

Movies

双包案; 铡包兔
京剧、曲艺、杂技艺术

Audio recording

Methodological framework

How DS supports EDI in GLAM structures?

Equality

- Accessibility:
easily shared and accessed;
reach underrepresented communities;
- Personal Engagement:
democratizes the archival process;
a sense of belonging and ownership.

Diversity

- Inclusion of Diverse Voices:
a wide range of perspectives are represented;
broadens the understanding of history and culture;
- Use of Multiple Media Formats:
resonate with different cultural backgrounds;
diverse ways of expression are respected and included.

Inclusion

- Community Participation:
empowers individuals and communities;
- Reflecting Marginalized Narratives:
marginalized narratives are brought to the forefront;
rectify historical imbalances;
build inclusive historical record.

Our expectations

We encourage local people:

- to *construct their own history*, to *choose their own digital presence* regarding the stories and present that as part of the collections to *build a more diverse and complete perspective* of the holdings;
- to *express their experiences and memories* about the city, important events, historical buildings, and their colonial occupiers;
- to enable them to *reevaluate their understanding of and engagement with the collections*, and how they might envisage and understand a framework to facilitate this;
- to raise awareness of the need for inclusivity and engagement with the wider community.

The framework brings the simple extension, enhancement, and enrichment of formats for expression, and also **facilitates structural changes** and an **evolution of the production, processing, and disseminating** of the historical narrative.

The framework aims to **raise awareness of the need for inclusivity and engagement, remove barriers to inclusion, and will go some way to remove the bias and implicit inequality** often found in GLAMs collections, particularly in areas with a significant post-colonial legacy.

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Thank you!

Shanghai Memory--Shanghai Cultural Collection Project: <https://scc.library.sh.cn/#/>

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